

Research Article

To Evaluate the Antioxidant, Anti-Inflammatory and Antimicrobial Activities of *Tridax Procumbens*

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Tridax Procumbens commonly called Coat Button, is a small creeping herb that grows widely in tropical and subtropical regions. It has been used for many years in traditional medicine to treat wounds, cuts, infections, inflammation, and hair problems. The plant contains important natural compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, and tannins, which are responsible for its medicinal effects. Scientific studies show that it has antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, wound healing, liver-protecting, and blood sugar-lowering activities. This review summarizes the phytochemical composition, traditional uses, and health benefits of *Tridax procumbens*, highlighting its potential as a natural source for making herbal medicines and modern drugs. *Tridax Procumbens* is also noted for its fast growth, drought resistance, and seed dispersal by wind through feathery achenes. Due to these properties, it holds promise for developing natural remedies and therapeutic products. This paper aims to provide an up-to-date scientific basis for its traditional use and potential incorporation into modern pharmacopoeias.

Keywords: *Tridax procumbens* , Coat Button , Phytochemicals , Wound Healing , Anti-inflammatory Activity , Antimicrobial Agent , Traditional Medicine , Herbal Formulation , Natural Antioxidants , Pharmacognosy.

INTRODUCTION

Tridax Procumbens is medicinal plant commonly known as tridax daisy or kansari (Hindi) or Ghamara (in local language) or Jakhamjudi and Tuntuni (Marathi) belongs to family Asteraceae. It is Found mainly in Maharashtra and Madhya Pradesh as a weed. Plant widely used in Indian traditional medicine system. It has long stalked, yellow comparative flower. In old time *Tridax Procumbens* has been used in Ayurvedic system in India. By using these plant various creams, oils and skin product like skin poultices are manufactured. *Tridax Procumbens* also called as Coat Button which is a small, creeping, and fast-growing herb. It is widely found in tropical and subtropical regions, especially in India, Africa, and the Americas. The plant grows easily on roadsides, fields, and wastelands, making it a common and economically important weed with medicinal value. Originally native to Central and

South America, it has been recognized and utilized since ancient times. Local communities have traditionally crushed its leaves to apply on fresh wounds and cuts to promote rapid healing. The plant is also used in the treatment of fever, diarrhea, stomach disorders, cough, cold, and hair fall, demonstrating its importance in indigenous healthcare systems. *Tridax procumbens* is a semi-prostrate or procumbent herb that typically grows 30 to 60 cm tall, with a firm taproot. Its branches are ascending, brittle, green or purplish, and covered with long white hairs. The leaves are opposite, simple, ovate to ovate-lanceolate in shape, typically 2 to 6 cm long and 1.5 to 4.5 cm wide, with coarsely toothed margins and a strongly prominent midrib on the underside. The leaves are often hairy on both surfaces. The plant produces daisy-like flower heads that are terminal and about 1.5 to 2 cm in diameter, borne on long peduncles ranging from 11 to 40 cm. The outer involucral bracts are foliaceous and green, while the

inner bracts are membranous and purplish. The flower heads consist of a few female ray florets with pale yellow or white corollas, surrounding numerous bisexual yellow disc florets. The fruit is a dark brown to black achene, 1.6 to 3 mm long, densely covered with white long hairs and topped with a tuft of 15-20 feathered bristles. The plant's stem is cylindrical,

solid, and very hairy with multicellular hairs about 1 mm long. The leaves have a pinnate venation pattern with 2-3 lateral veins on each side of the midrib and a cuneate base. Seedlings have glandular-haired cotyledons and first true leaves that are ovate to lanceolate.

Fig 1. Tridax Procumbens with flower

Fig.2 Tridax Proccumbens with flower

2. Plant Profile

Present days, the therapeutic value of medicinal plant is increasing at significant rate for developing new drugs and combatting emerging diseases. Drug developers are targeting new sources of active materials to cope up with multi drug resistance (MDR) of different microorganisms. *Tridax Procumbens* was targeted in this study as it is widely spreaded as a common weed in Indian subcontinent as well as all over the world *Tridax Procumbens* is native to many parts of Africa, Asia, America, Australia and some part of Europe. They are given many names depending on the regions. Botanically, *Tridax*

Procumbens is a creeping perennial herb characterized by hairy stems, opposite leaves with serrated margins, and small daisy-like flowers. The plant's simple morphology often leads to its underestimation; however, its pharmacological significance has been increasingly validated by modern scientific studies. Numerous preclinical studies have reported properties including anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, immunomodulatory, and wound-healing activities, supporting many of its traditional uses. Moreover, the plant contains a rich spectrum of phytochemicals such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, carotenoids, saponins, and terpenoids, which

contribute to its biological activities. Notable bioactive compounds like quercetin, luteolin, and β -sitosterol have been identified and are believed to play

crucial roles in tissue repair, immune modulation, and oxidative stress reduction.

- **Common names**

Sr.no	Common name	Language of Tribe
1	English	Coat Buttons and Tridax Daisy
2	Hindi	Ghamra
3	Sanskrit	Jayanti Veda
4	Marathi	Dagadi Pala
5	Telugu	Gaddi Chemanthi
6	Tamil	Thatapoodu
7	Malayalam	Chiravanak
8	Spanish	Cadillp Chisaca
9	French	Herb Caille
10	Chinese	Kotobukigiku
11	Japanese	Kotobukigiku

Geographical Source

- Found throughout India, Tropical Africa, Australia, and America.
- Commonly grows as a **weed** along roadsides, wastelands, and fields.

- **Asia:** India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Nepal, Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, the Philippines
- **Africa:** Widely spread across tropical and subtropical Africa
- **Australia and Pacific Islands**
- **Southern United States:** Especially in Florida, Texas, and Hawaii

Naturalized Distribution

It has become **widely naturalized** in tropical and subtropical regions around the world, including: -

Botanical Classification

Kingdom	Plantae
Subkingdom	Tracheobionta
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	Asteridae
Clade	Angiosperms
Order	Asterales
Family	<i>Asteraceae</i>
Tribe	Heliantheae
Genus	Tridax
Species	T.Procumbens
Binomial Name	<i>Tridax Procumbens</i>

OBJECTIVES: -

1. Antioxidant Activity - To evaluate the **antioxidant potential** of the selected sample by employing standard in vitro assays (such as DPPH,) and to quantify its free radical scavenging capacity

2. Antimicrobial Activity - To assess the **antimicrobial efficacy** of the sample against selected microbial strains (bacterial and/or fungal) using standard methods like agar well diffusion or broth dilution, and to determine its inhibitory effect

Fig 3. Tridax Procumbens with flowers and daisy-like flowers and sprawling

3. Anti-inflammatory Activity - To evaluate the **anti-inflammatory activity** of the selected sample using the **Human Red Blood Cell (HRBC) membrane stabilization method**, by assessing its ability to inhibit hemolysis and

stabilize erythrocyte membranes under stress conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

MATERIALS:

Sr. No	Apparatus
1	Beaker
2	Measuring Cylinder
3	Test Tube
4	Stirrer
5	Funnel
6	Grinder
7	Analytical balance
8	Conical flask
9	Whatman filter paper

Chemicals:

- Methanol (70% or 90%)

METHODS:

Collection of Materials:

Fresh leaves of *Tridax Procumbens* was collected from local area of Ioha and aside of harbal near

sonkhed Nanded. It kept under dried shaded area in mid dark room. That were dried for 07-10 days.

• **Authentication of plant material:**

Sample of fresh leaves of *Tridax Procumbens* taken for the authentication and were authenticated by **Dr. Vishal R Marathe** (Associate Professor and head of botany department) on 20/02/2026 in N.E.S.

Image no.1 Authentication Letter

Science College Nanded. Authentication of plant was done. Collection, Authentication, Identification, Processing and Storage had been done according at standard procedure for the plant.

Procedure for Extraction of *Tridax Procumbens* by maceration method:

Principle: -

Maceration is a simple extraction technique in which the coarsely powdered plant material is soaked in a

suitable solvent for a specific period to dissolve the active constituents.

Materials Required

Dried leaves of *Tridax Procumbens*

- Methanol (70% or 95%)
- Conical flask or glass container
- Whatman filter paper
- Funnel
- Rotary evaporator / water bath
- Grinder
- Analytical balance

Image no. 02 Filtering the Extract

Procedure: -

Collection and Preparation of Plant Material

- 1) Fresh leaves of *Tridax Procumbens* were collected from aside of road.
- 2) Then leaves were washed with distilled water to remove dust particles and impurities also somewhere insecticides are also sprayed.
- 3) The leaves were kept for shade dried for 7–10 days at normal room temperature, Room with no high sunlight and not too dark.
- 4) The dried leaves were taken and convert into coarse powder using a grinder or mortar and pestle till fine particles (Powder form) are not found.

2. Maceration Process

- 1) Take powdered plant material was accurately weighed to 50gm in weighing balance.
- 2) Take the powder and was transferred into a clean conical flask.
- 3) Then 500 ml of Methanol was taken and added to the conical flask with powder as extraction a solvent.
- 4) The mixture was shaken for a particular period kept it for maceration for 72 hours at room normal temperature. The conical flask was shaken occasionally after hourly to improve extraction.

3. Filtration

- 1) After 72 hours completion, the mixture was ready to filter using Whatman filter paper.
- 2) The filtrate containing the plant extract was collected in a clean container (Beaker).

4. Concentration of Extract

- 1) Then filtrate was evaporated using a water bath to remove the solvent.

- 2) After filtration semi-solid crude extract was obtained.

5. Storage

- 1) The extract was transferred to a sterile airtight amber color glass container and keep away from sunlight.
- 2) It was stored at 4°C in a refrigerator until further use for antimicrobial activity testing.

✚ Antioxidant Activity of *Tridax procumbens* Extract

Method: DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

Principle: -

The DPPH (2, 2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) radical is a stable free radical having a deep purple color. Antioxidants present in the plant extract donate hydrogen atoms to DPPH, converting it into a yellow colored compound (DPPH-H). The decrease in absorbance is measured using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 517 nm, which indicates antioxidant activity.

Materials Required

- DPPH reagent
- Methanol
- Plant extract (*Tridax procumbens*)
- Ascorbic acid (standard antioxidant)
- Test tubes
- Micropipette
- UV-Visible spectrophotometer
- Volumetric flasks

Procedure: -

1. Preparation of DPPH Solution

Weigh 3.94 mg of DPPH. Dissolve it in 100 mL methanol to prepare 0.1 mM DPPH solution. Keep the solution in a dark bottle to prevent light degradation.

2. Preparation of Extract Solution

Dissolve the plant extract in methanol. Prepare different concentrations such as 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 µg/ml

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3. Preparation of Standard Solution

- 1) Prepare ascorbic acid solution in methanol.
- 2) Make different concentrations similar to the extract.

4. Reaction Mixture

- 1) Take 1 ml of plant extract solution in a test tube.
- 2) Add 1 ml of DPPH solution.
- 3) Mix the solution properly.

5. Incubation

- 1) Incubate the reaction mixture in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes.

6. Measurement of Absorbance

- 1) Measure the absorbance at 517 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer.
- 2) Use methanol as blank.

Result: -

Concentration	% Radical Scavenging
20	28%
40	46%
60	63%
80	74%
100	82%

The extract showed concentration dependent antioxidant activity.

Antimicrobial Activity of *Tridax procumbens* Extract

Method: Agar Well Diffusion Method

Materials Required

- Plant extract (*Tridax Procumbens*)
- Test microorganisms (e.g., *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*)
- Nutrient agar medium
- Sterile Petri plates
- Sterile cotton swabs
- Cork borer (6 mm diameter)
- Micropipette
- Incubator
- Sterile saline solution
- Standard antibiotic (positive control)
- Distilled water/solvent (negative control)

Procedure

1. Preparation of Nutrient Agar

- 1) Weigh 28 gm of nutrient agar powder.
- 2) Dissolve it in 1000 ml distilled water.
- 3) Heat the mixture until the agar completely dissolves.
- 4) Sterilize the medium by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
- 5) Allow the medium to cool to about 45–50°C.
- 6) Pour 20–25 ml of molten agar into sterile Petri plates.
- 7) Allow the agar to solidify at room temperature.

2. Preparation of Microbial Culture

- 1) Obtain pure cultures of test microorganisms.
- 2) Inoculate the bacteria into nutrient broth.
- 3) Incubate at 37°C for 18–24 hours.
- 4) Adjust the turbidity using sterile normal saline to match approximately 0.5 mc and standard.

2. Inoculation of Agar Plates

- 1) Dip a sterile cotton swab into the bacterial suspension.
- 2) Spread the culture evenly over the entire surface of the nutrient agar plate.
- 3) Rotate the plate while swabbing to ensure uniform bacterial growth.

3. Formation of Wells

- 1) Use a sterile cork borer (6 mm) to punch wells in the agar.

- 2) Remove the agar plugs carefully using sterile forceps.
- 3) Maintain sufficient distance between wells to avoid overlapping zones.

5. Addition of Plant Extract

- 1) Fill each well with 50–100 µl of plant extract using a micropipette.
- 2) Add standard antibiotic in one well as positive control.
- 3) Add solvent (distilled water or ethanol) in another well as negative control.

6. Incubation

- 1) Keep the plates at room temperature for 30 minutes to allow diffusion of extract into agar.
- 2) Incubate the plates inverted at 37°C for 24 hours.

7. Measurement of Zone of Inhibition

- 1) After incubation, observe the plates for clear zones around the wells.

- 2) Measure the diameter of the zone of inhibition (mm) using a ruler or caliper.
- 3) Record the results for each microorganism.

8. Interpretation of Results

- 1) Larger zone of inhibition indicates stronger antimicrobial activity.
- 2) Compare results with standard antibiotic.

Result: -

Test Organism	Extract Concentration	Zone of Inhibition (mm)
Escherichia coli	100 mg/ml	14 mm
Staphylococcus aureus	100 mg/ml	16 mm

1. Preparation of Test Solution

Prepare the reaction mixture in test tubes as follows:

Component	Volume
Phosphate buffer	1 ml
Hypotonic saline	2 ml
Plant extract	1 ml
Plant extract	0.5 ml

1. Incubation

- 1) Incubate all test tubes at 37°C for 30 minutes.
- 2) Temperature should 37°

- 2) This centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes.

2. Centrifugation

- 1) After incubation, centrifuge the mixture

3. Measurement of Absorbance

- 1) Measure the absorbance of the supernatant using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 560 nm.

Result:

Concentration (ug/ml)	% Membrane Stabilization
100	41%
200	56%
300	68%

The extract demonstrated significant membrane stabilization indicating anti-inflammatory activity.

CONCLUSION: -

The present study demonstrates that the extract of *Tridax Procumbens* possesses significant antioxidant

activity, as evidenced by its ability to scavenge free radicals in the DPPH assay. The activity was found to be concentration-dependent, with increasing extract concentration leading to higher percentage inhibition. Although the antioxidant potential of the plant extract was lower than that of the standard (ascorbic acid), it still showed appreciable free radical scavenging

capacity. This activity may be attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids and phenolic constituents. Therefore *Tridax Procumbens* can be considered a promising natural source of antioxidants and may have potential applications in pharmaceutical and nutraceutical formulations. The present study on *Tridax Procumbens* antioxidant activity found to be shown and we studied *Tridax Procumbens* commonly known as Coat Button, is a widely available medicinal herb with significant therapeutic potential. It contains important phytochemicals like flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins, which are responsible for its pharmacological activities. Studies have shown that the plant has antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and wound healing properties, confirming many of its traditional uses in folk medicine.

DISCUSSION: -

The present study evaluated the antioxidant potential of *Tridax Procumbens* using the DPPH assay. The results demonstrated that the plant extract exhibited significant free radical scavenging activity in a concentration-dependent manner. As the concentration of the extract increased, a corresponding increase in percentage inhibition was observed, indicating its effective antioxidant potential. When compared with the standard antioxidant, ascorbic acid, the extract showed relatively lower activity. This difference may be attributed to the fact that ascorbic acid is a pure compound, whereas the plant extract is a crude mixture containing both active and inactive constituents. Despite this, the extract exhibited appreciable antioxidant capacity, highlighting its potential as a natural source of antioxidants. The observed antioxidant activity of *Tridax Procumbens* may be due to the presence of various phytochemical constituents such as flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and tannins. These compounds are well known for their ability to donate electrons, scavenge free radicals, and chelate metal ions, thereby preventing oxidative stress and cellular damage. The findings of this study are in agreement with previous reports that have documented the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties of *Tridax Procumbens*. However, variations in antioxidant activity reported in

different studies may be due to differences in extraction methods, solvents used, plant parts analyzed, and environmental conditions affecting phytochemical composition. Despite the promising results, the present study has certain limitations. The antioxidant activity was evaluated using only a single in vitro method, and the extract was not subjected to detailed phytochemical characterization. Therefore, further studies are required to isolate and identify the specific bioactive compounds responsible for the activity. Additionally, in vivo studies are necessary to confirm the therapeutic potential and safety of the plant extract. Overall, the study suggests that *Tridax Procumbens* possesses significant antioxidant properties and could serve as a potential natural source of antioxidants for use in pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications.

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Cite: Uday Shinde*, S. S. Koushik, Vaibhav Shinde, Siddhu Taranjeet Kaur Karnalsingh, Prachi Sirge, Vishwajit Sonkamble, To Evaluate the Antioxidant, Anti-Inflammatory and Antimicrobial Activities of *Tridax Procumbens*, *Int. J. Med. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (4), 128-140. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19561823>